

4D-printed composite structures for space applications : towards modular multi-axis structural shape-changing

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Context : autonomy

Terrae Novae 2030+ Strategy Roadmap - ESA

A. Tribble The space environment and its impact on spacecraft design, in *31st Aerospace Sciences Meeting, AIAA* (1993).

R. Thirsk et al. The space-flight environment: the International Space Station and beyond, *CMAJ* 180 12, 1216-1220 (2009)

Harsh environments such as space require **low energy consumption** and **low maintenance needs**

<https://bsgn.esa.int/business-in-space/business-in-space-growth-network/terrae-novae/>

Space technologies are submitted to **large thermal fluctuations**

~ temperature range : **300°C**

Racca, G. D. Moon surface thermal characteristics for moon orbiting spacecraft thermal analysis. *Planetary and Space Science* 43, 835–842 (1995).
Donohue, J. H. & Frisch, H. P. Thermoelastic Instability of Open-Section Booms, NASA (1969).
Foster, C. et al. Solar-array-induced disturbance of the Hubble Space Telescope pointing system. *Journal of Spacecraft and Rockets* 32, 634–644 (1995).

Autonomous and passive motion generation

Twisting module

Le Duigou, A. et al. Bioinspired 4D Printed Tubular/Helicoidal Shape Changing Metacomposites for Programmable Structural Morphing. *Advanced Materials Technologies* **10**, 2400237 (2024).

ESA/UBS patent

Bending module

Assembly

Biomimetics : top-down approach

Biological model : crinoids

Pictures credits : N. Améziane

Crinoids : deep-sea invertebrates

Deep-sea & space :
Harsh environments

Ability to **move passively**, in response to the environment

Credits : N. Améziane

Biomimetics : top-down approach

MCTs : Mutable Collagenous Tissues

- Non-contractile collagenous ligaments
- Extracellular matrix with contractile properties upon activation by chemicals

Donovan et al. 1989

Passive flexibility, in response to environment variations

Variable stiffness

Biomimetics : top-down approach

Abstraction : translation in materials science terms

Stimulus ON

Stimulus ON

Abstraction : 4D-printing

3D-printing

Shape-morphing materials

Kim, Y. et al. Printing ferromagnetic domains for untethered fast-transforming soft materials. *Nature* **558**, 274–279 (2018)

Continuous fibres deposition

Pichard, P.L. et al. Efficient energy-dissipative bioinspired architected composite materials with high mechanical properties. *Additive Manufacturing* (2025).

4D-printing

Use of the **environment** as a **source of energy** to induce movement

Wang, Q. et al. Programmable morphing composites with embedded continuous fibres by 4D printing. *Materials & Design* **155**, 404–413 (2018).

Biomimetics : top-down approach

Manufacturing : 4D-printing process

3D-printing enables the manufacturing of an infinite number of ossicle topologies

Basalt fibers embedded in a PA12 matrix

Column formed by stacked ossicles

Original device allowing for continuous fibre deposition on curved surfaces

Continuous fibers deposition enables perfect control of the anisotropy

Biomimetics : top-down approach

Crinoid-inspired actuator concept

Oven

Camera

Améziane, N. & Roux, M. Environmental control versus phylogenetic fingerprint in ontogeny: The example of the development of the stalk in the genus *Guillecrinus* (stalked crinoids, Echinodermata). *Journal of Natural History* **39**, 2815–2860 (2005).

Parametric study

- Nonlinear relation between the ossicles diameter and the bending ability of the column
- Importance of thermal inertia and of the resisting moment resulting from ossicle weight
- Influence of the diameter variation limited to the transient regime

Modular assembly concept

Rotation actuator

Bending actuator

Tuning parameters :

- Ossicle number
- Ossicle geometry
- Fiber quantity

Tuning parameters :

- Active/passive matter ratios
- Aspect ratio
- Fiber angle

Modular assembly

Composition of complex trajectories by assembling units with targeted functions

Biomimetics : top-down approach

Technical Problem

Biological model

Functions identification

Potential application

Manufacturing

Abstraction

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Thank you for your attention

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